
The Effect of Marketing Communication on Patient Trust and Loyalty in Healthcare Facilities: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT: Marketing communication in healthcare services has shifted from a purely informative approach to an integrated relational strategy aimed at building patient trust and loyalty. However, its effectiveness in improving patient satisfaction and loyalty remains empirically varied. This study aims to review recent literature to confirm the effectiveness of marketing communication strategies in enhancing patient satisfaction and loyalty within healthcare facilities. This study employed a systematic literature review approach guided by the PRISMA framework. Articles were retrieved from five databases (ProQuest, PubMed, ScienceDirect, Google Scholar, and EBSCO) published between 2021 and 2026. Inclusion criteria consisted of original research articles available in full-text that examined the impact of marketing communication on patient trust, satisfaction, and loyalty. A total of 12 eligible articles were analyzed qualitatively. The review findings indicate that marketing communication significantly influences patient satisfaction and indirectly affects loyalty through the mediation of trust and service quality. Message consistency, information transparency, and digital communication integration were identified as key determinants in strengthening long-term relationships between healthcare institutions and patients. Marketing communication plays a strategic role in enhancing patient satisfaction and loyalty, particularly when integrated with service quality improvement and institutional reputation management.

KEYWORDS: Marketing communication, Patient trust, Patient satisfaction, Patient loyalty, Healthcare services, Relationship marketing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the past decade, the healthcare industry has experienced increasingly competitive dynamics at both national and global levels. The transformation of healthcare systems, the digitalization of health information, the rise in patient literacy, and shifts in healthcare consumer behavior have compelled healthcare institutions to adopt more strategic and value-based managerial approaches (1). Hospitals with a large base of loyal patients can rely on them for long-term services, including outpatient care, inpatient treatment, and other medical services. In a highly competitive industry environment, numerous factors influence customer loyalty. In the healthcare service industry, patient loyalty is a critical determinant of a hospital's sustainability and ability to survive amid intense competition (2). Marketing communication is no longer perceived merely as a promotional activity but rather as a strategic instrument for building long-term relationships between healthcare facilities and patients.

Patient trust in hospital services can be understood as the extent to which patients believe in the healthcare provider's ability to meet their expectations and rely on the competence of the service provider. Some hospitals tend to focus primarily on marketing processes, sales, and brand awareness as strategies to increase revenue. However, this study seeks to examine the role of Public Relations (PR) as a component of marketing communication, where PR functions to deliver effective messages about hospital services, health campaigns, and institutional advantages. In addition, high-quality service delivery contributes to fostering patient trust in the quality of hospital services, which in turn builds patient loyalty(3).

Marketing communication in the healthcare sector has distinct characteristics compared to other commercial industries, given that healthcare services are intangible, involve high levels of patient engagement, and contain significant elements of risk and uncertainty(4). Therefore, the effectiveness of marketing communication is not solely determined by the ability to convey service information but also by its capacity to build perceptions of credibility, transparency, and empathy. In service marketing literature, consistent and integrated communication plays a significant role in shaping perceived quality, fostering trust, and encouraging customer loyalty behaviors (5).

Public Relations plays a vital role in building patient loyalty and supporting hospital revenue growth. Through effective communication strategies, reputation management, and the utilization of technology, PR can create sustainable relationships between hospitals and patients. Public Relations is a management function aimed at establishing and maintaining mutually beneficial

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relationships between an organization and its publics. PR plays a crucial role in fostering effective two-way communication, which enhances understanding and trust between hospitals and patients. In the hospital context, PR functions not only as an information disseminator but also as a mediator connecting the hospital with the broader community (6).

In practice, hospitals frequently encounter complaints and grievances from patients and the public. Patient complaints refer to suggestions, criticisms, or objections communicated verbally or in writing to the hospital. Negligence and inadequate medical facilities are common issues that negatively affect the public image of healthcare services (7). Patients may perceive the quality of care as inadequate, often attributing it to the performance of healthcare human resources

Community members are more likely to develop loyalty when they receive high-quality service from hospitals. Increased patient loyalty is aligned with increased hospital revenue. Furthermore, relationships between the institution, the community, and stakeholders improve as information management and service quality are effectively maintained (8). That effective public relations strategies can enhance patient satisfaction and loyalty, thereby contributing to increased hospital revenue. This finding indicates that PR is not merely a communication function but also a strategic management tool within hospital administration (9).

Patient trust is a fundamental determinant of the sustainability of relationships between patients and healthcare providers (10). Trust reflects patients' confidence in the professional competence, integrity, and commitment of healthcare institutions to ensure patient safety and well-being. In healthcare settings, trust is formed not only through clinical experiences but also through effective, accurate, and responsive communication. When marketing communication consistently and authentically conveys service value, patients' perceived risks can be minimized, thereby strengthening their confidence in the healthcare institution (4).

Patient loyalty in the healthcare context is not limited to repeat visits but also encompasses long-term commitment, institutional preference, and positive word-of-mouth recommendations. Loyalty serves as a key indicator of operational sustainability for healthcare facilities, particularly amid increasing service options and institutional competition. Therefore, understanding the mechanisms linking marketing communication, patient trust, and patient loyalty constitutes a strategic issue that requires comprehensive examination based on contemporary literature.

2. RESEARCH METHODS

This study employed a systematic literature review (SLR) approach to synthesize recent empirical evidence regarding the effectiveness of marketing communication in enhancing patient trust and loyalty in healthcare services. The literature search was conducted across five reputable databases: ProQuest, PubMed, ScienceDirect, Google Scholar, and EBSCO. A combination of keywords and Boolean operators was used to ensure a systematic and comprehensive search strategy, including: marketing communication, patient trust, patient loyalty, public relations, kepercayaan pasien, and loyalitas pasien. These terms were combined using AND and OR operators to refine the search results.

To ensure the relevance and quality of the included studies, predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied. The inclusion criteria were: (1) articles published between 2020 and 2026, (2) written in English or Indonesian, (3) classified as original empirical research, (4) available in full-text, and (5) explicitly examining the relationship between marketing communication and patient trust or loyalty in healthcare settings. Articles that did not meet these criteria, including review papers, editorials, and studies with incomplete data, were excluded.

The study selection process followed the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines. The initial search identified 472 articles, which were screened based on titles and duplicates, resulting in 102 potentially relevant studies. Subsequently, 63 full-text articles were assessed for eligibility. After applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 12 articles were included in the final analysis. Data from the selected studies were analyzed using a descriptive qualitative synthesis approach. Each article was examined based on research objectives, methodology, variables, and key findings. A thematic synthesis was then conducted to identify patterns and relationships between marketing communication, patient trust, and patient loyalty. This approach enabled the development of a structured and evidence-based interpretation of the role of marketing communication in healthcare services.

To ensure the rigor of the review, this study utilized multiple databases, applied systematic selection criteria, and documented the review process transparently in accordance with PRISMA guidelines.

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Figure 1. PRISMA Flow Diagram of Article Selection Process

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the 21 articles that met the inclusion criteria, 10 articles were selected to be presented in Table 1 as examples of relevant research findings the selected studies had to specifically examine the impact of marketing communication on patient trust and loyalty within healthcare facilities

Table 1. Results of Article Data Mapping

No	Author(s) (Country)	Title	Method	Findings	
1	(Andriani et al, 2025) (Indonesia)	Peran Marketing dalam Meningkatkan Kepuasan Pasien di Rumah Sakit Muhammadiyah Surakarta.	Relationship Loyalitas Pasien: Dimediasi oleh Kepuasan Pasien: Studi pada Rumah Sakit Muhammadiyah Surakarta.	This study employed a quantitative method using a survey approach by distributing online questionnaires to 204 respondents. The collected data were processed and analyzed using SmartPLS software among the research variables.	The results indicate that social bonding and trust have a significant and positive effect on patient satisfaction. Furthermore, patient satisfaction was found to mediate the relationship between trust and loyalty; however, it did not mediate the effects of communication and commitment on loyalty.
2	(Mellena et al, 2025) (Indonesia)	Pengaruh Pelayanan, Kepercayaan, dan Kepuasan Pasien terhadap Loyalitas Pasien di Rumah Sakit Arcamanik.	Kualitas Komunikasi dan Kepercayaan Pasien terhadap Dokter di Rumah Sakit Arcamanik.	This study was designed as a quantitative study involving a sample of 102 non-BPJS patients at RS Hermina Arcamanik. Data were analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) with the SmartPLS version 4 application.	The findings indicate that service quality, brand trust, and trust in doctors have a positive effect on patient satisfaction and loyalty. However, a unique finding emerged in which the communication variable had a positive effect on satisfaction but exerted a negative effect on loyalty.
3	(Zahara, 2024) (Indonesia)	The Influence of Marketing Communications and Quality of Service on National Health Insurance		This study employed a descriptive and explanatory survey method involving National Health Insurance	The findings indicate that both marketing communication and service quality have a significant effect on JKN patient satisfaction.

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No	Author(s) (Country)	Title	Method	Findings
		Patient Satisfaction Participating in the National Health Insurance Registered at the Pratama Hegar Clinic, Bandung Regency.	(JKN) patients at Klinik Pratama Hegar. Quantitative data analysis was conducted to examine the partial and simultaneous effects of marketing communication and service quality on patient satisfaction.	Partially, service quality was found to have a more dominant influence in determining the level of patient satisfaction compared to the marketing communication variable.
4	(Puspasari, 2021) (Indonesia)	Pengaruh Bauran Pemasaran Jasa dan Kepercayaan Pasien terhadap Loyalitas Pasien (Studi Kasus di Poli Spesialis Rematologi Rumah Sakit Hasan Sadikin Bandung).	This study employed a descriptive and explanatory survey method. Data were collected through questionnaires, interviews, and direct observations of patients at the Rheumatology Specialist Clinic. Data analysis was conducted using path analysis techniques.	The results indicate that improvements in the performance of the marketing mix (9Ps) and patient trust simultaneously have a positive effect on patient loyalty. The marketing mix and trust contributed 16.4% to patient loyalty, while the remaining proportion was influenced by other factors beyond the scope of the research model.
5	(Sharma et al, 2022) (Nepal)	Customer Loyalty and Relationship Marketing in the Nepalese Telecommunications Sector.	The research design adopted was descriptive and causal-comparative to identify key variables within the telecommunications industry. Primary data were collected through a structured questionnaire using a five-point Likert scale administered to mobile phone users and subsequently analyzed using quantitative techniques.	The findings reveal a positive relationship between customer loyalty and the variables of trust, communication, commitment, and conflict handling. Trust and commitment were identified as the primary factors exerting the strongest influence on customer loyalty within the practice of relationship marketing in the Nepalese telecommunications industry.
6	(Hariyanti et al 2023) (Indonesia)	The Influence of Social Media Marketing on Patient Visit Intention Mediated by Brand Awareness.	This study employed a quantitative observational method with a cross-sectional design. Data were collected via Google Forms from 96 followers of the social media account of RSU Universitas Muhammadiyah Malang and analyzed using Partial Least Squares (PLS).	The results indicate that social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on patients' visit intention. This relationship is significantly mediated by brand awareness, suggesting that social media marketing efforts enhance brand recognition, which in turn increases patients' intention to visit.
7	(Meilia et al 2021) (Indonesia)	Analisis Strategi Komunikasi Pemasaran Rumah Sakit Bunda Sejati Terhadap Loyalitas Pasien Rawat Jalan Pada Masa Pandemi COVID-19.	This study employed a descriptive qualitative method. The researchers analyzed the marketing communication strategy using the Input framework (Man, Money, Machines, Method), Process (SWOT analysis), and Output (social and personal factors) to understand the phenomenon of patient loyalty amid the global pandemic situation.	The findings indicate that, overall, the marketing communication strategy had been implemented in accordance with service standards; however, there were constraints related to the limited number of marketing personnel. In addition, external factors—such as government policies and public anxiety during the pandemic—were identified as major obstacles in maintaining patient loyalty.
8	(Amelia et al 2024) (Indonesia)	The Influence of Marketing Mix, Service Quality, and Image on Trust and Satisfaction of Inpatients in Makassar City Hospitals.	This study employed a quantitative method by collecting primary data through questionnaires from 215 hospitalized patients. Data were analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with	The results indicate that service quality and hospital image have a positive and significant effect on patient trust, while the marketing mix has a positive but not significant effect on trust. Conversely, the marketing mix was found to have a

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No	Author(s) (Country)	Title	Method	Findings
			SmartPLS version 4 to examine the relationships among variables.	direct, positive, and significant impact on inpatient satisfaction.
9	(Zahara, 2024) (Indonesia)	The Influence of Marketing Communications and Quality of Service on Patient Satisfaction Participating in the National Health Insurance Registered at the Pratama Hegar Clinic, Bandung Regency.	This study employed a descriptive and explanatory survey method involving National Health Insurance (JKN) patients at Klinik Pratama Hegar. Data were analyzed quantitatively to examine the partial and simultaneous effects of marketing communication and service quality on patient satisfaction	he results indicate that marketing communication and service quality have a significant effect on JKN patient satisfaction. Partially, service quality was found to have a more dominant impact in determining patient satisfaction levels compared to the marketing communication variable.
10	(Nugraha et al , 2024) (Indonesia)	Analisis Pengaruh Komunikasi Pemasaran, Kualitas Pelayanan dan Kepercayaan terhadap Loyalitas Pelanggan Produk Uniqlo.	This study employed a quantitative approach with a population consisting of consumers who had visited Uniqlo stores at least twice. A sample of 93 respondents was collected and analyzed using regression techniques to examine the effect of independent variables on customer loyalty.	The findings, both partially and simultaneously, demonstrate that marketing communication, service quality, and trust have a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty. The Adjusted R Square value of 56.4% indicates that these three variables make a substantial contribution to the formation of customer loyalty.
11	(Syamsudin & Wirawan, 2021) (Indonesia)	Pengaruh Komunikasi Pemasaran, Kepercayaan dan Penanganan Keluhan terhadap Loyalitas Nasabah Tabungan di PT. BPR Syariah Mitra Mentari Sejahtera Ponorogo.	This study employed a quantitative approach with a causal research design. Primary data were collected through an online questionnaire administered to 130 Islamic bank customers. Multiple linear regression analysis was used to test the research hypotheses.	The results indicate that marketing communication, trust, and complaint handling simultaneously have a significant effect on customer loyalty. Marketing communication was identified as the most dominant factor influencing customer loyalty in the Islamic banking institution
12	((Tüfekçi & Eser, 2023) (Sydney)	The health and social needs of public dental patients.	This study employed an anonymous cross-sectional survey design involving public dental patients aged over 18 years in the Sydney Local Health District. The research instrument consisted of a structured questionnaire covering demographic characteristics, binary (yes-no) questions, and Likert-scale items to broadly identify patients' social and health needs within the clinical dental setting.klinis kedokteran gigi.	The findings indicate that the majority of patients (99%) considered oral health to be very important to their overall health; however, significant challenges in accessibility were identified. A total of 43% of respondents reported difficulties in accessing general healthcare services, and a high demand for additional social support services such as housing assistance and welfare support was observed. These results suggest that public dental patients often experience complex health and social needs that extend beyond oral health issues.

Marketing communication has a significant influence on the satisfaction of National Health Insurance (JKN) patients, although service quality remains the more dominant determinant. This indicates that communication functions as a reinforcement of patients' perceptions of the quality of services received. The marketing mix contributes to satisfaction but does not always directly shape trust. During crisis situations, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, systematic marketing communication strategies were able to maintain patient loyalty despite resource limitations. Furthermore, digitalization has expanded the dimensions of marketing communication, demonstrating that social media marketing significantly influences patients' visit intentions through the mediation

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of brand awareness, thereby emphasizing the importance of two-way interaction in fostering patient engagement. Patient trust is understood as a psychological construct reflecting confidence in the competence, integrity, and commitment of healthcare institutions. Trust significantly influences both satisfaction and loyalty and serves as a mediator in the relationship between relational variables and loyalty. Two primary dimensions of trust are identified: trust in the institutional brand and trust in physicians, both of which contribute positively to the formation of patient loyalty. This suggests that loyalty in healthcare services is shaped through psychological processes involving both personal and institutional dimensions simultaneously.

DISCUSSION

Although trust has a significant influence on patient loyalty, its contribution is relatively limited, indicating the presence of other factors that also affect loyalty (9). The consistency of the relationship pattern among communication, trust, and loyalty is further supported by cross-sector studies demonstrating that effective communication enhances trust and ultimately strengthens customer loyalty. Conceptually and empirically, marketing communication in healthcare occupies a strategic position as a key determinant in building trust and patient loyalty; however, its influence is often indirect and dependent on interactions with service quality and patient experience variables (11).

From a services marketing perspective, marketing communication in healthcare is more complex than in consumer goods sectors due to the characteristics of services, which are intangible, inseparable, heterogeneous, and high risk (7). In this context, communication functions not only as a means of delivering information but also as an uncertainty reduction mechanism for patients facing medical, financial, and psychological risks. Recent literature emphasizes that marketing communication must be positioned as an integral part of institutional quality management and reputation strategies rather than merely as a transactional promotional activity (4).

Conceptually, the functions of marketing communication in healthcare services can be classified into informative, persuasive-reputational, relational, and risk-reduction dimensions. In the informative dimension, communication provides clarity regarding clinical procedures, costs, facilities, and healthcare professionals' competencies. Studies indicate that marketing communication significantly influences JKN patient satisfaction, suggesting that information clarity contributes to positive patient evaluations pasien (3). In the persuasive and reputational dimension, institutional image significantly affects trust, making message consistency a crucial factor in strengthening perceptions of hospital credibility. The influence of communication on trust can be explained through three primary mechanisms: message consistency across channels (social media, customer service, physicians, and official websites), information transparency, and interactive engagement (2).

The relationship between marketing communication and patient loyalty may be either direct or indirect. Some studies have found that marketing communication significantly influences loyalty with substantial explanatory power (9). However, in healthcare settings, this effect more frequently operates through mediation mechanisms. Research indicates that satisfaction mediates the relationship between trust and loyalty, while communication positively affects satisfaction but does not always directly influence loyalty (1).

Evaluation of communication effectiveness suggests that its success largely depends on integration with actual service quality, message consistency across channels, human resource competence, and adaptation to external contexts. In crisis situations such as a pandemic, communication effectiveness is also influenced by external factors, including government policies and public anxiety. Digital communication through social media has been shown to effectively increase visit intention through brand awareness (11). Nevertheless, the potential overpromising effect where discrepancies arise between communicated messages and actual experiences may negatively affect loyalty. Therefore, strengthening empirical evidence through longitudinal designs and more comprehensive structural models is necessary to optimize marketing communication as a strategic instrument for sustainably building patient trust and loyalty (11).

4. CONCLUSION

The results of the literature review indicate that marketing communication in healthcare services plays a strategic role in building patient trust and loyalty through mediating mechanisms, particularly satisfaction and trust. Its effectiveness depends on message consistency, information transparency, actual service quality, and the integration of digital communication. Therefore, communication should be positioned as an integral component of institutional quality and reputation strategies to ensure sustainable patient loyalty.

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